

Supplemental Materials

Appendix 1: Bayesian model parameters and specification

Observed data consisted of:

- $\{i\}$ = Set of Philadelphia ZIP codes that have reported ≥ 1 case of COVID-19
 Y_i^* = Number of observed positive SARS-CoV-2 tests in ZIP code i
 T_i = Total population in ZIP code i
 A_i = Area deprivation index in ZIP code i
 D = Diagonal matrix representing the number of contiguous neighbors
 W = Binary spatial weights matrix

Models consisted of:

ZIP code prevalence candidate models:

- Model 1: Base:* $\text{Logit}(r_i) = \eta_0 + \eta_1 * A_i$
True prevalence of COVID-19 in ZIP code i , conditioned on A_i .
- Model 2: Unstructured random effect:* $\text{Logit}(r_i) = \eta_0 + \eta_1 * A_i + u_i$
True prevalence of COVID-19 in ZIP code i , conditioned on A_i and unstructured random effect u_i .
- Model 3: Spatially structured random effect:* $\text{Logit}(r_i) = \eta_0 + \eta_1 * A_i + v_i$
True prevalence of COVID-19 in ZIP code i , conditioned on A_i and spatially structured random effect v_i .
- Model 4: Convolution model:* $\text{Logit}(r_i) = \eta_0 + \eta_1 * A_i + u_i + v_i$
True prevalence of COVID-19 in ZIP code i , conditioned on A_i and unstructured random effect u_i and the spatially structured random effect v_i .

Count of infected: $Y_{.t_i} \sim \text{Binom}(T_i, r_i)$
Number of positive SARS-CoV-2 tests in ZIP code i based on true prevalence, r .

Observed infected if infected: $Y_{.tp_i} \sim \text{Binom}(T_i - Y_{.t_i}, \text{SN}_i)$
Number of true positive SARS-CoV-2 tests in ZIP code i based on ZIP code surveillance SN.

Observed infected if not infected: $Y_{.fp_i} \sim \text{Binom}(Y_{.t_i}, 1-\text{SP})$
Number of false positive SARS-CoV-2 tests in ZIP code i based on ZIP code surveillance SP.

Observed cases: $Y_i^* \sim (Y_{.tp_i} + Y_{.fp_i})$
Observed cases are a function of observed infected if infected model and observed infected if not infected model. We let a variable $E_i = Y_{.t_i} - Y_i^*$ to capture the difference between the true and observed cases.

Priors consisted of:

$\text{SN}_i \sim \text{Beta}(14.022, 9.681)$ Sensitivity of inclusion in surveillance data corresponding to a median SN of 59% with 5- and 95-percentiles of 42% and 75%, respectively.

SP	$\sim \text{Beta}(100, 3.02)$	Specificity of inclusion in surveillance data corresponding to a median SP of 95% with 5- and 95-percentiles of 94% and 99%, respectively.
η_0	$\sim \text{Norm}(-3.5, 0.5)$	True prevalence of COVID-19 (logit scale) when $A_i=0$ corresponding to a mean prevalence of 3% with a standard deviation of 2%.
η_1	$\sim \text{Norm}(0.04, 0.04)$	Effect of A_i on true prevalence of COVID-19 (logit scale) where each standard deviation increase in ADI is associated with a change in prevalence of 6% (95% CI: -1%, 14%).
u_i	$\sim \text{Norm}(0, \tau)$	Random error (unstructured) in ZIP code i
v_i	$\sim \text{MNorm}(0, \tau * (D - \varphi * W))$	Error described by spatial dependency in ZIP code i .
φ	$\sim \text{Unif}(0, 0.99)$	Spatial autocorrelation with an uninformative prior.
τ	$\sim \text{Gamma}(1, 0.1)$	Precision of the random parameters with a weak prior.

Appendix 2: Diagnostic plots of select parameters from Model 1

Trace – sn[1]

Trace – sn[4]

Trace – sn[7]

Trace – sn[10]

Trace – sn[13]

Trace – sn[16]

Trace – sn[19]

Trace – sn[22]

Trace – sn[25]

Trace – sn[28]

Trace – sn[31]

Trace – sn[34]

Trace – sn[37]

Trace – sn[40]

Trace – sn[43]

Trace – sn[46]

Trace – eta0

Trace – tau

Trace – r[3]

Trace – r[6]

Trace – r[9]

Trace – r[12]

Trace – r[15]

Trace – r[18]

Trace – r[21]

Trace – r[24]

Trace – r[27]

Trace – r[30]

Trace – r[33]

Trace – r[36]

Trace – r[39]

Trace – r[42]

Trace – r[45]

Trace – deviance

Density – deviance

Appendix 3: Diagnostic plots of select parameters from Model 2

Trace – sn[1]

Trace – sn[4]

Trace – sn[7]

Trace – sn[10]

Trace – sn[13]

Trace – sn[16]

Trace – sn[19]

Trace – sn[22]

Trace – sn[25]

Trace – sn[28]

Trace – sn[31]

Trace – sn[34]

Trace – sn[37]

Trace – sn[40]

Trace – sn[43]

Trace – sn[46]

Trace – eta0

Trace – tau

Trace – r[3]

Trace – r[6]

Trace – r[9]

Trace – r[12]

Trace – r[15]

Trace – r[18]

Trace – r[21]

Trace – r[24]

Trace – r[27]

Trace – r[30]

Trace – r[33]

Trace – r[36]

Trace – r[39]

Trace – r[42]

Trace – r[45]

Trace – deviance

Density – deviance

Appendix 4: Diagnostic plots of select parameters from Model 3

Trace – sn[1]

Trace – sn[4]

Trace – sn[7]

Trace – sn[10]

Trace – sn[13]

Trace – sn[16]

Trace – sn[19]

Trace – sn[22]

Trace – sn[25]

Trace – sn[28]

Trace – sn[31]

Trace – sn[34]

Trace – sn[37]

Trace – sn[40]

Trace – sn[43]

Trace – sn[46]

Trace – eta0

Trace – tau

Trace – r[3]

Trace – r[6]

Trace – r[9]

Trace – r[12]

Trace – r[15]

Trace – r[18]

Trace – r[21]

Trace – r[24]

Trace – r[27]

Trace – r[30]

Trace – r[33]

Trace – r[36]

Trace – r[39]

Trace – r[42]

Trace – r[45]

Trace – deviance

Density – deviance

Appendix 5: Diagnostic plots of select parameters from Model 4

Trace – sn[1]

Trace – sn[4]

Trace – sn[7]

Trace – sn[10]

Trace – sn[13]

Trace – sn[16]

Trace – sn[19]

Trace – sn[22]

Trace – sn[25]

Trace – sn[28]

Trace – sn[31]

Trace – sn[34]

Trace – sn[37]

Trace – sn[40]

Trace – sn[43]

Trace – sn[46]

Trace – eta0

Trace – tau

Trace – r[3]

Trace – r[6]

Trace – r[9]

Trace – r[12]

Trace – r[15]

Trace – r[18]

Trace – r[21]

Trace – r[24]

Trace – r[27]

Trace – r[30]

Trace – r[33]

Trace – r[36]

Trace – r[39]

Trace – r[42]

Trace – r[45]

Trace – deviance

Density – deviance

